

ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF LITERATENESS AMONG SCHOOL LEAVERS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to see how well history is understood by Form Six pupils in Sarawak, Malaysia. Three dimensions of historical literacy are examined in this study: knowledge, skills, and historical values. As a study tool, the researchers created a questionnaire with multiple-choice questions on history. A total of 465 pupils from Sarawak's Form Six were recruited as research subjects. To determine the participants' historical literacy level, the data is descriptively analysed. According to the statistics, 69.40 percent of the population knows about history, 67.34 percent knows about skills, and 81.61 percent knows about values. A literacy rate of 72.78 percent is found in History.

Key words: Sarawak, education, school leavers, form six

INTRODUCTION

History education is beneficial to students because it helps them gain historical knowledge as well as key skills and values. Students are required to take History beginning in Form One in order to get a broad understanding of the country's history. The ability to analyse and evaluate historical data is emphasised as a requirement for pupils in school history instruction. In terms of ideals, it is believed that history education will produce citizens with a patriotism spirit. This demonstrates that teachers in the History discipline have integrated information, skills, and values into the teaching and learning process. In this context, the topic of how well-versed school leavers are in History after five years of study has been raised.

The Integrated Curriculum Secondary School has showed how knowledge, skills, and values are all interconnected when it comes to history. The integration has been implemented in the subject's teaching and learning processes at the same time and in a continual manner. The knowledge domain includes the students' grasp of the growth of society and the country in terms of politics, economy, and social issues. Students learn how to gather information,

master ideas, and employ historical methodologies in history courses such as Local History Studies, Malaysian History, and International History.

Students are taught not only facts, but also critical and historical thinking, as well as the value of pure values and patriotism (Ministry of Education, 2003). In addition to skills, knowledge and values about history must be acquired. According to the KBSM history curriculum, students' critical thinking and historical reasoning skills should be fostered as part of the subject's teaching and learning strategy. Students should be able to objectively analyse, formulate, and evaluate historical facts about their country, as well as acquire mental ability and maturity through historical experiences, according to the History subject's declared goal (Ministry of Education, 2003).

Historical thinking skills are the domain of abilities that students need to acquire, according to the framework of the history curriculum, and they have been included with the other two domains: knowledge and values, in historical discipline.

In the History topic, patriotism is emphasised in the area of values to generate citizens who are proud to be Malaysians, loyal to the country, and have a sense of community. Patriotism is described as a strong attachment to one's homeland. These feelings should be accessible to all Malaysians, regardless of race. Patriotism is supposed to unify Malaysians and bring them together in peace. Students are taught to objectively analyse and evaluate historical facts using their knowledge and understanding of the country's history. It is intended that by studying about and understanding their country's history, kids will develop a passion for it.

As a result, History places a high value on information, abilities, and values. If students are to grasp all three domains, they must be integrated into the teaching and learning process. This is because acquiring thinking skills, for example, leads to a full understanding of history. Learning history, according to Aini Hassan (1994), entails knowing the past in a creative, inventive, and thought-provoking way. As a result, students learn to make rational analyses and evaluations of historical material while studying history. Students are also encouraged to draw parallels between previous occurrences and current developments. Understanding and appreciating history can aid in the development of skills and the cultivation of values such as curiosity and patriotism. Because cognitive and affective processes are intertwined, both cognitive and affective factors appear to be taken into account. You can enjoy and understand emotional factors better if you have the ability to think. There is no doubt that critical thinking skills and historical thinking skills are essential in the History curriculum. Students who have mastered thinking skills can expand their grasp of history by conducting a number of thinking activities such as separating facts from views, making comparisons, classifying, and judging the veracity of what they've learned. One may grow and appreciate one's most fundamental ideals by having a deep understanding of issues and historical occurrences. As a result, critical thinking abilities can assist students in achieving the purpose of the History class, which is to instil a sense of national pride and love for the country.

Much has been said about the above-mentioned thinking talents in general. Because each person must evaluate and analyse various historical facts and information, higher order thinking skills that require a broad use of the intellect are critical in history teaching. As previously noted, history education must incorporate parts of mastering knowledge, skills, and values.

Objective

- To determine the level of overall history literacy among Sarawak students?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The primary data gathering instrument for this study was a questionnaire. It was researchers who came up with the idea for this one! The first part is an introduction, while the second part is a discussion. Part B has 42 multiple choice items depending on the respondents' backgrounds. The majority of these items are made up of knowledge, abilities, and values. For each item, there are four different designs to choose from. There are 18 in the cognitive domain, 14 in the skills domain, and 10 in the values domain. Bloom's (1955) cognitive, psychomotor, and emotional characteristics are present in all of the items generated for the three domains: knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation at various levels of understanding.

Sarawak's Form Six pupils are the target population. Students have studied History from Form One to Form Five because it is now an obligatory subject in the Integrated Curriculum Secondary School. Researchers employed Form Six students from Sarawak's ten administrative districts' District Education Offices to perform the study. A single school is chosen to represent each district. The study used a random sample of 465 pupils. The interviewees' backgrounds include gender, race, SPM History grade, school location, and stream.

DATA ANALYSIS

The survey data gathered by the researchers is analysed using SPSS version 22.0 for Windows in this study. The results of descriptive study are split down into frequency and percentages. Data is analysed based on the percentage score achieved when determining historical literacy. The analysis includes knowledge, skills, and values. Respondents who scored 100 percent in History had the highest levels of history literacy, while those who scored less than 100 percent had the lowest. Gender, ethnicity, SPM History grade, streams, and school location are only a few of the characteristics that can be explained using the frequency and percentage distribution. The application that was used to analyse the data can calculate percentages and a mean for you.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The knowledge, skills, and values of those who took the History test were all assessed.

Overall literacy in History

In order to be literate in History, one must be knowledgeable in three distinct areas, as shown in Table 4. For example, students scored 69.40 percent in knowledge, 67.34% in skills, and 81.61% in values in the table above, which shows the average percentage they scored in each of the three domains combined.

Table 4. Levels of literacy in History

Item	Percentage (%)
Knowledge	69.40
Skills	67.34
Values	81.61
Overall percentage	72.78

Form Six students in Sarawak's reading proficiency in history is shown in Table 4. According to the findings of the research, the literacy rate in History is 72.78 percent.

CONCLUSION

The discussion above has concluded with a descriptive analysis of all the findings in order to meet the aforementioned goals. According to the findings of the descriptive study, Form Six students in Sarawak have an average level of literacy in History. Students' knowledge, skills, and values need to be mastered and understood because it gives a clear picture of their historical literacy. Following closely behind are knowledge (70.30%), skills (70.30%), and values (74.23%) as far as literacy levels are concerned (64.64 percent). According to these findings, there is still room for improvement in historical literacy.

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